

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HITCHMAN****FIRST NAME: ELEANOR****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR ACADEMIC WRITING

1. Which of the following statements about citing webpages in Turabian style is correct?

- Website citations should include the author, title, owner or sponsor of the site, date of publication, modification or revision and URL.¹**
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- Website citations should include the author, title, owner or sponsor of the site, date of publication and URL.
- Website citations should include the author, title, owner or sponsor of the site, publication date and modification or revision.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers or Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 62.

2. Which of the following statements is correct regarding the use of sources when researching a topic?

- Using secondary sources to keep current research updated and find other viewpoints and models for your research is acceptable.²**
- It is acceptable to use secondary sources only to find different views.
- For quality research, it is necessary to use primary sources of information only.
- For quality research, you should use primary sources of information to keep up with current research and secondary sources to find other points of view and models for your research and analysis.

3. Why do you include a warrant when constructing arguments during academic research?

- When you think a reader might reject your claim because a reason supporting it might be seen as irrelevant.³**
- When you consider, a reader might reject your claim because the reason supporting it is factually incorrect.
- When you think the reason supporting the claim is not sufficiently evidenced.
- You should always include a warrant; otherwise, the reader will not understand your arguments.

4. Which of the following statements is correct about using abbreviations for names, titles, and other terms used frequently in your paper in Turabian-style academic writing?

² Ibid., 62.

³ Ibid., 56.

- You may use abbreviations by giving the complete term on the first reference, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses, and for subsequent references, you can use the abbreviation.⁴**
 - You can use the abbreviation throughout the paper if you include a list of abbreviations at the beginning.
 - You can use the abbreviation throughout the paper if you give the whole term on the first reference of each new chapter.
 - Abbreviations should not be used in academic writing.
5. What's the difference between a colon and a semicolon?
- A colon introduces information set up by the previous clause and is typically used before a list, example, or explanation. A semicolon is used to join related independent clauses together in the same sentence without conjunction.⁵**
 - A semicolon introduces information set up by the previous clause and is typically used before a list, example, or explanation. A colon is used to join related independent clauses together in the same sentence without conjunction.
 - A colon introduces information set up by the previous clause and is typically used in the same sentence without conjunction. A semicolon joins related independent clauses, for example, before a list or explanation.
 - There is no difference, and either can be used indiscriminately.

⁴ Ibid., 353.

⁵ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma., *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 18.

6. Which of these following situations do not require citation?
- When you are stating well-known facts that are common knowledge.** ⁶
 - When you quote exact words from a source.
 - When paraphrasing ideas associated with a specific source, even if you do not reproduce exact words from it.
 - When using opinions, data, or methods attributable to any source you consulted.
7. Which of the following is the correct format for using lists in Turabian academic writing?
- Lists of short items (without main verbs) should be introduced by a full sentence with the following features: introductory colon, no initial capitals, no punctuation or comma after each item and a full stop at the end.** ⁷
 - Lists of short items (without main verbs) should be introduced by a full sentence with the following features: introductory semicolon, initial capitals, no punctuation or comma after each item and a full stop at the end.
 - Lists, where each item completes the introductory sentences, should: begin with the introductory semicolon; each item should be labelled with the appropriate bullet, number or letter; end with a semicolon and close with a full stop.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers or Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 140..

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition (European Commission, 2021), 60-62.

- Lists, where each item completes the introductory sentences, should: begin with the introductory semicolon; each item should be labelled with the appropriate bullet, number or letter; end with a colon and close with a full stop.
8. What is the difference between a summary and a synthesis in a literature review?
- A summary shares the key points from an individual source and then moves on and summarises another source. A synthesis combines information from multiple sources and includes a literature analysis.⁸**
- A synthesis shares the key points from an individual source, and a summary combines information from multiple sources.
- A summary and synthesis are the same: synthesis is just the term used in academic writing.
- A summary shares the key points from an individual source, and a synthesis combines information from multiple sources.
9. Which reflexive questions are not helpful when analysing and interpreting findings in qualitative research?
- Have I removed any disconfirming evidence that might undermine the findings of my research?⁹**
- Have I made any interpretive arguments that are not grounded in my data?

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe., *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 385.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 641.

- Have I misinterpreted the findings, and if so, in what ways?
- Do I fully understand the world of my participants to correctly interpret their words?

10. Which statement applies to quantitative research?

- The research should be conducted under controlled conditions.**¹⁰
- Only small sample sizes are required.
- The research should take place within natural and everyday conditions.
- The researcher designs a flexible and creative framework.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018.

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¹⁰ Ibid.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.